

The Study of Relationship Between the Processes of Creating Technological and Marketing Innovations on the Example of Russia

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Abstract: The purpose of the paper is to find an answer to the following questions: how the technological and marketing are innovation related, and to what extent is marketing innovation critical for the implementation of technological one? The study considers two possible types of relationship: complementarity and interdependence of these processes. The former type of relationship characterises the existence of the opportunity for the process interaction, and the latter one means its implementation. The concepts of the core and sub-core of the innovation process are used to find the answer to these questions. The set of enterprises involved in technological innovation is classified as a technology-innovative core; at the same time, the population of enterprises engaged in the marketing innovation shapes a marketing-innovative core. In turn, the enterprises that act simultaneously in both technological and marketing innovation form an innovative sub-core. The existence of a non-empty innovative sub-core means that complementarity of technological and marketing innovative processes takes place, i.e. there is room or potential for their interaction. If the potential is realised at least partially, we will consider the processes (or their corresponding activities) as interdependent. Those innovative active enterprises are forced to create marketing innovations promoting technological ones. In other words, to establish process interdependence, it is sufficient to demonstrate that marketing innovations contribute significantly greatly to promoting technologically new or significantly improved products. The investigation proves that for some Russian enterprises, these two just mentioned innovative processes are interconnected. The nature of such interconnection is investigated; namely, it finds out that marketing innovations are created and used to promote not well-known, but new for the market products. A comparative analysis of the strategies of using marketing innovations and their effectiveness for enterprises of Russian and foreign ownership is carried out.

Keywords: technological and marketing innovations, complementarity of processes, interaction of processes, promotion of technological innovations

1. Introduction

The term “innovation” traditionally refers to technological advances in new products or production processes. This approach dominated in the economic and management literature for a long time since Schumpeter’s first work in 1934 (Schumpeter and Opie, 1961). With the formation and further development of innovation theory, the field of research expanded, in particular, with the addition “non-technological” types of innovation, i.e. marketing and organisational ones, began to be actively studied (OECD 2005, 2019).

The importance of the study of marketing innovation was emphasized in the 60s of the last century (Levitt, 1960). However, research related to this topic became widespread later in the 21st century. At the same time, it is worth noting that the studies of creating technological and marketing innovations are often unrelated in the literature. It can be justified if companies promote technologically new products mainly using standard marketing methods, but they prefer marketing innovations to expand sales of conventional products.

Nevertheless, according to economic practice, these types of innovation activities are often interrelated. In particular, a situation is possible when technological innovations, namely product innovations, may cause changes in marketing strategies requiring the creation and use of marketing innovations (Boer and During, 2001). Below we will try to find out, taking into account statistics, the answers for the questions:

Whether there is a significant relationship between the processes of creating technological and marketing innovations in Russia? How are the processes related? What is the structure of their links?

In doing so, we will adhere to the following outline. In the beginning, the concepts of complementarity and interconnection of the processes of creating technological and marketing innovations will be given in conjunction with the ideas of innovative cores and their sub-core. Then these terms are used to formulate and prove the necessary and sufficient conditions for the existence of the relationship between the processes of

creating technological and marketing innovations. Finally, the strategies of the behaviour of enterprises which created technological and marketing innovations will be studied for Russian and foreign ownership.

2. The methodology of the study

The purpose of this study is to find answers to the questions mentioned above. The study considers two possible types of interrelationships between these processes to respond to the questions. These are complementarity and direct interaction. For determining the conditions under which these types of relationships occur, it is necessary to address the methodology of research of National innovation system (NIS), proposed in (Golichenko 2011, 2016). According to the methodology, it makes sense to distinguish a core of intensity for each innovation system process. The core is the minimal part of the production process on which it is concentrated. The part is located on various entities (organisations) whose activities are at least partially related to the considering processes. In other words, the core of intensity determines the set of resources available to the process at the given time. Therefore, it determines the current growth capacity of the process by involving unused core resources.

Since the two processes, the technological and marketing innovation ones, are the subject of the study, their intensity cores need to be considered below. The first of these cores relevant to the creation of technological innovations is called a technology-innovative core, and the second referred to generating marketing innovations is named a marketing-innovative core. The innovation cores of these processes determine the set of resources available to the innovation processes at the given time. In other words, they characterise the current growth potential of the innovation process (Golichenko, 2011).

The second notion actively used below is a sub-core of these innovation processes, which we call below the "innovative sub-core". Its carriers are the companies that are active simultaneously in the development of both technological and marketing innovations. In other words, the innovative sub-core represents the intersection of the innovative cores of the processes of creating technological and marketing innovations.

At the sub-core enterprises, the processes essentially supplement each other, i.e. they are complementary (Golichenko, 2014). The complementarity of processes means that there is room or potential for the interaction of these processes. If this potential is (at least partially) implemented, that is, activities to create technological and marketing innovations are interconnected (or interdependent), the corresponding processes will be called as conjugate ones.

The interconnection between the processes of creating technological and marketing innovations in enterprises, in particular, means that enterprises carrying out technological innovations are forced to develop marketing innovations for promoting technologically innovative products. The opposite is also possible when new marketing ideas generate the requirement for technological variations of the product.

Some studies are establishing the existence of a potential for interaction between technological and marketing innovation. In our terms, that means the non-emptiness of the sub-core. Among them, the article (Kijek, 2013), which analyses the innovative activity of industrial enterprises in Poland in 2008 – 2010. The regression analysis helps the author of the article to conclude that companies active in product innovation are more inclined to innovate in marketing. The research (Ilić et al., 2014) is also concerned to some extent, with an interaction potential of the processes of interest to us. In the article, the estimate based on a sample of 310 enterprises in Serbia shows that 73% of them used at least one type of non-technological innovation. In contrast, technological innovations took place for 61.5% of enterprises.

At the same time, it is worth noting that modern literature rarely highlights the issues of the interdependence of the processes. Among the studies in which these issues are addressed in some way, the research (Schubert, 2010) should be pointed out. Here, in particular, it is shown that when German firms are active in both technological and marketing innovations, their sales of innovative products are up. The fact indirectly indicates the presence of a conjugation effect of the processes of interest to us. Similar results can be found in the paper (Schmidt and Rammer 2013), which shows that in many firms that had technological innovations the utilisation of marketing innovations accompanies the increase in sales and reduction of innovation costs. The authors also conclude that the probability of creating technologically innovative products is higher in firms that use marketing innovations.

One of the disadvantages of current research in the field of marketing and technological innovation is the only use of micro-level data analysis. The statistics of groups of enterprises united by some attribute, for example, belonging to the same form of ownership or the same size class, are seldom studied. As a rule, no attempt is made to find out to what extent whether the potential for the interaction of processes is achieved. Moreover, finally, a sufficiently complete set of characteristics of the processes of innovation creation and dissemination processes is not taken into account.

And finally, the methodological framework just mentioned should also include the algorithm implemented in the next section. It is related to the study of the relationship between the two types of innovation and consists of two following steps. At the first one, we are looking for an area (sub-core) where either of the two types of innovation activities exists simultaneously. At the second step, we determine the sub-core and propose a hypothesis of the interconnection of these types of innovation activities for this area. To prove the hypothesis, we calculate some significant benchmarks characterising these innovation activities in the area. If the values of the corresponding indicators differ significantly for the sub-core and cores of two types of innovation activities, it means that there is a strong relationship between these types of innovation on the sub-core. If the changes are insignificant or absent at all, we can conclude that the two types of innovation are separated, and do not affect each other, i.e. they are not interconnected. Besides, if the hypothesis is correct, changes in benchmarks in one way or another have to reveal differences in the behaviour strategies of the enterprises under consideration.

3. Relationship between technological and marketing innovation in Russia

The issue of the relationship between creating technological and marketing innovations is relevant today. Usually, it is believed that marketing innovation accompanies technologically innovative products. However, in Russia, as shown in (Golichenko and Fakhrudinova, 2014, Gorodnikova et al, 2014,), marketing innovations have significantly smaller distribution than technological ones, i.e. a technology-innovative core is much larger than an innovative sub-core. Therefore, the question arises: are the processes of creating marketing and technological innovations connected on the sub-core or do they exist separately? In other words, it is necessary to confirm or refute the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1. There is an interdependence of the processes of creating technological and marketing innovations in Russia.

Necessary and sufficient conditions. The necessary condition for the interdependence of the processes, that is, the existence of their interaction, is their complementarity. The complementarity means that two sets have a non-empty intersection. One of the sets consists of the enterprises having carried out technological innovations, and the other contains companies having created marketing innovations. In other words, a necessary condition for the interrelation of processes is the non-emptiness of their innovative sub-core.

Before proceeding to formulate sufficient conditions for the existence of the interdependency, it is worth pointing out that there are two ways to divide the output of the enterprises of the sub-core.

On the one hand, it is worth taking into account that two disjoint parts compose the output of an enterprise. The first of them includes technologically innovative products (TIP), and the second is associated with products that are non-innovative technologically. On the other hand, the same output is a sum of two other unrelated parts, for one of which the marketing innovations (MI) are necessary to promote the output to the market, and for the other, they are not being used. It is easy to see that the following intersections of the output parts described above are possible.

- Marketing innovative products are a part of technologically innovative output (Figure 1).
- Marketing innovative products are part of both technologically innovative and non-innovative output (Figure 2).
- Marketing innovative products are part of conventional, technologically non-innovative products (Figure 3).

The fulfilment of 1) or 2) is a sufficient condition for the interdependence of technological and marketing innovation.

Figure 1: The interconnection of technological and marketing innovation (the use of marketing innovations to promote only technologically innovative products)

3.1 Proof of the interconnection between the processes.

For what follows, it is useful to introduce the notions of a “pure” technology-innovative core and a “pure” marketing-innovative core. To define such “pure” cores let us exclude the sub-core from the innovative cores mentioned above. Consequently, we get the two following types of pure cores:

- 1) “pure” technology-innovative core consisting of enterprises that only carried out technological innovations;
- 2) “pure” marketing-innovative core whose enterprises created merely marketing innovations.

Figure 2: The interconnection of technological and marketing innovation (The use of marketing innovations to promote both technologically innovative and conventional, non-innovative products)

Below only “pure” cores are considered. Therefore, for the sake of simplicity, the attribute “pure” is omitted, that is, instead of the terms “pure technology-innovative core” and “pure marketing-innovative core”, the expressions “technology-innovative core” and “marketing-innovative core” are respectively in use below. To prove the interdependence (or interconnection) of technological and marketing innovation, let us show that the necessary and sufficient conditions for it are met. As mentioned above, the necessary condition is the complementarity of the processes, that is, the non-emptiness of the innovative sub-core. The fact that the sub-core is not empty is proved by the data of Russian statistics (Form No. 4 - Innovation). According to these data, the sample of interest to us contains enterprises that simultaneously carried out technological and marketing innovations. For the period from 2013 to 2017, the number of such enterprises was 500-600 units. Further, enterprises that have carried out technological or marketing innovations will be denoted as TIE or MIE, respectively.

Figure 3: The lack of interconnection of technological and marketing innovation (The use of marketing innovations to promote only conventional, non-innovative products)

The fulfilment of sufficient conditions 1) and 2) (see Figures 1 and 2) can be proved by contradiction. To do this, let us assume that condition 3) is true and show the opposite. The proof consists in the analysis of transitions from each innovative core to the sub-core. If there are no significant shifts in the values of the control indicators for at least one of these transitions, it means that the processes we are interested in are not interdependent, i.e. condition 3) is satisfied.

As key control indicators are taken the following ones:

- 1. share of costs of product and process innovations in total costs for technological innovations;
- 2. cost-intensity of product innovation equal to the ratio of the costs of product innovation to the sales of technologically innovative products;
- 3. share of technologically radical, innovative products in total sales of technologically innovative output;
- 4. cost-intensity of marketing innovation equal to the ratio of the costs of the marketing innovations to the output sales increasing due to the marketing innovations.

The source of information for calculating all of these key control indicators is data from Russian statistics (“Form No.4 Innovation. Information on innovation activities of the organization”).

Here and further technologically radical innovative products mean technologically innovative products that are new to the firm and the market. The indicators are considered in relation to enterprises of Russian and foreign ownership forms. Under the enterprises of foreign ownership in the Russian market, we mean the company with the participation of foreign ownership. In other words, the set of enterprises considering include both Russian-foreign and foreign-owned companies.

Let us proceed to the analysis of indicators just outlined.

3.1.1 The costs of product and process innovations in the total expenditure on technological innovations.

For Russian-owned enterprises belonging to the technological innovation core, almost three-quarters of the spending on technological innovation is accounted for product innovation and one-quarter is due to process innovations (see Figure 4). Nevertheless, for the sub-core of Russian property, the costs of product and process innovations are approximately equal. As far as foreign-owned enterprises are concerned, their transition from the technological innovation core to the sub-core cause a decrease in the share of costs for product innovations (from 37% to 27%) and an increase in the share of costs for process innovations (from 63% to 72%). Thus, regardless of the form of ownership, the shares for product and process innovations in total innovation expenditures are significantly changing while proceeding from the technological innovation core to the sub-core.

Source: Based on Russian statistics Database: Form No.4 Innovation. Information on innovation activities of the organization.

Figure 4: Ratio of costs for product and process innovation for various forms of ownership at the innovation core and sub-core, 2013-2017

3.1.2 Cost-intensity of product innovation

Cost-intensity of product innovation For Russian-owned firms of the technological and innovative core and sub-core, the cost-intensity of product innovation indicators are 19.6% and 63%, respectively (Figure5). Besides, for foreign-owned enterprises, the value of the cost intensity indicator, moving from a technology-innovative core to the sub-core, drops from 6.7% to 5.9%. The reasons for this difference in shifts in indicator values are investigated in the next section.

Source: Based on Russian statistics Database: Form No.4 Innovation. Information on innovation activities of the organization.

Figure 5: Cost-intensity of product innovation for various forms of ownership at the innovation core and sub-core, 2013-2017

3.1.3 New for the market, newly introduced and modernised products in the total volume of technological innovation output

For Russian-owned enterprises, the transition from a technologically innovative core to a sub-core significantly increases the share of new products for the market (1.7 times from 11.4% to 19.6%). The other two components of innovative output do not change so significantly (see Figure 6). A different dimension and magnitude of changes in the relevant indicators concerns enterprises of foreign ownership. For this form of ownership, the share of new products for the market decreases by two times (from 2.8% to 1.3%) after this transition. At the same time, the percentage of newly introduced or significantly technologically improved products in the sales increases 1.8 times (from 41.6% to 74.2%), and the share of modernised products decreases by 2.3 times (from 58.4% to 25.8%).

Source: Based on Russian statistics Database: Form No.4 Innovation. Information on innovation activities of the organization.

Figure 6: Ratios of new to the market, newly introduced and modernised innovative products, 2013-2017

Recapitulating the main points of the analysis of the three above-mentioned indicators, one can conclude that the economic activity of creating marketing innovations has a significant impact on the process of creating technological innovations. Moreover, the dimension of this influence depends significantly on whether the form of ownership is Russian or foreign.

3.1.4 Cost-intensity of marketing innovation.

The values of indicators of the cost-intensity at the pure marketing innovative core and sub-core differ significantly (Figure 7). When switching to the sub-core, MIEs of Russian ownership increase the cost of creating marketing innovations by 6.5 times (from 1.1% to 7.1%). Foreign-owned MIEs reduce their cost-intensity by two times (from 4.4% to 2.1%).

Source: Based on Russian statistics Database: Form No.4 Innovation. Information on innovation activities of the organization.

Figure 7: Cost-intensity of marketing innovation, 2013-2017

In other words, technological innovations have a considerable impact on the creation of marketing innovations at the sub-core. At the same time, the nature and depth of the impact depend largely on the type of ownership.

Summing up the results of the section, in accordance with the methodology section it is worthwhile to note that innovative processes in the field of marketing and technology are interdependent. Moreover, the interdependence works in both directions: the former ones affect the latter and vice versa. In other words, our assumption that technological and marketing innovations are not related to the sub-core is incorrect. It allows us to assert that sufficient conditions are met; that is, there is a correlation between the processes of creating technological and marketing innovations. Therefore, Hypothesis 1 is correct.

4. Behaviour strategies of enterprises depending on the forms of ownership

The distinctions in the relationships of the technological and marketing innovation for different forms of ownership was found above. This distinction stems from differences in the behaviour strategies of companies of the considered property forms. The first of these differences relates to the choice of the type of innovative products supported new marketing technologies. The second one is due to the choice of the type of market for which enterprises create marketing innovations to stimulate demand for their conventional products.

4.1 Strategy for creating and promoting product technological innovations on the market

First, let us recall that, the structure of expenditures on technological innovations changes, when moving from the technology-innovative core to the sub-core, changes for both forms of ownership, i.e. the share of expenditures on process innovations increases. Our research shows that this is due to the need to strengthen support to product innovation from process innovation. This structural shift is accompanied by a change in the costs-intensity of innovative products (see Figure 5). Moreover, these shifts are oppositely directed for the considered forms of ownership. If, for the Russian property, the costs-intensity increases from 19.6% to 63%, for foreign-owned enterprises, it decreases slightly: from 6.7% to 5.9%.

At the same time, it is not difficult to see that the cost-intensity of process innovations in both the technology-innovative core and sub-core is significantly higher for Russian-owned enterprises compared to enterprises of foreign ownership. This fact one can partly attribute to the greater efficiency of foreign-owned production. Also it is worth noting that switching from the innovative core to sub-core increases dramatically this gap. Indeed,

according to the data shown in Figure 5, the cost-intensity of product innovation for Russian companies is almost three times higher than for companies with foreign participation on the technology-innovative core in 2013-2017; however, this ratio becomes equal to eleven times on the sub-core. The question arises: what explains this phenomenon?

To find the answer to this question, refer to the data in Figure 6. As it follows from them, there is a significant growth in the cost-intensity for Russian-owned enterprises, which can be explained by the increased complexity of product innovation, that is, the radicalisation of the process. Indeed, according to Figure 6, for Russian-owned enterprises, there is a sharp surge in the share of products of that are new to the market and, at the same time, technologically new or improved. The share increases from 11.4% (on the technology-innovative core) to 19.6% (on the sub-core). Market promotion of such "radically new products" requires the intensification of the processes of creating marketing innovations. Consequently, it is not surprising that, according to Figure 7, the cost-intensity of marketing innovation of Russian-owned enterprises is almost seven times higher on the sub-core than on the marketing-innovative core.

For foreign-owned enterprises, the picture is different: in passing to the sub-core, a decrease in the cost-intensity of product innovation is observed (see Figure 5). This drop is accompanied by a more than twofold decrease in the share of both "radically new" and modernized products (Figure 6). The decrease in the share of radically new products may cause a decrease in the cost-intensity of marketing innovation in approximately the same proportions.

Such peculiarities of behaviour of foreign-owned enterprises can be explained by the fact that they are more export-oriented, i.e. to world markets than Russian enterprises. Therefore, even radical new products of Russian-owned enterprises may not have sufficient market novelty for foreign markets. At the same time, another part of the production of foreign-owned enterprises classifying by Russian statistics as technologically new or significantly improved one, but not new to the (domestic) market of these enterprises, may turn out to have a significant novelty for the Russian market.

However, being already advanced in the foreign market, the production may not require deep marketing innovations for its promotion in the Russian market by foreign-owned enterprises. For them, a minor upgrade of already proven and well-established marketing methods may be sufficient to promote the production. It is relevant to the fact that of the low level of cost-intensity of marketing innovation of foreign-owned enterprises (it is more than three times lower than the corresponding value for Russian enterprises on the sub-core). Thus, for each of the two forms of ownership, the sub-core is more advanced in product innovation compared to the technology-innovative core. Enterprises of each form of ownership use marketing innovations to promote their radically new products. At the same time, enterprises of foreign ownership are in a better position than Russian enterprises, since promoting products new to the Russian market, but known to the world market, they can save on the cost of branding innovations.

4.2 Strategies for selecting areas of activity in marketing innovation

Enterprises involved in the process of creating marketing innovations face the problem of choosing the direction of the process organizing. The selection of the direction depends on the purpose of future use of these innovations. There are two main directions: 1) to conquest local markets of conventional (non-innovative) products 2) to promote a technologically new or significantly improved product to the local market.

To find out how this choice depends on the form of ownership, let us turn to the indicator of the cost-intensity of the marketing innovation. For each of the two property groups under consideration, we will consider the values of this indicator on a marketing-innovative core, whose enterprises do not participate in creating technological innovations, and on the innovation sub-core, whose companies are directly involved in both processes of creating technological and marketing innovations.

4.2.1 The market for traditional, non-innovative products

The use of marketing innovations to win a regional market of traditional products is relevant for enterprises of foreign ownership. It confirms the fact that for foreign-owned MIEs that are not involved in creating technological innovations, the cost-intensity of marketing innovation is four times higher than for Russian-owned enterprises (4.4% versus 1.1%, see fig.7). Such a significant difference is because the first group of

enterprises loses out in the knowledge of the local market. This circumstance makes the enterprises of the group spend high expenditures on marketing innovations. These innovations allow them to attract more local consumers to purchase their products.

4.2.2 Market for innovative products

At the same time, if Russian-owned enterprises pass to the innovative sub-core, i.e. they create technological innovations along with marketing ones, the cost-intensity of marketing innovation increases by 6.5 times (from 1.1% to 7.1%, see fig.7). As mentioned above, the increased attention paid to the marketing innovation in the sub-core of Russian-owned enterprises because the marketing innovations contribute greatly to promoting radically new products to the market (technologically new or significantly improved and new to the market ones).

5. Conclusion

A theoretical scheme, which allows determining the presence or absence of interconnection of two innovative processes on the sub-core enterprises was proposed and implemented. The implementation of this scheme to industrial enterprises of the Russian Federation made it possible to establish the following.

Even though marketing innovations in Russia have a much smaller distribution area compared to technological ones, innovative processes in the field of marketing and technology are strongly related.

The necessary and sufficient conditions under which the strong links between the processes arise are determined. The requirements are quite logical and straightforward. So it was accepted that the necessary conditions should include the presence of a non-empty innovative sub-core, and as the most obvious and logical sufficient condition must be the fact that the output sold due to involving new methods of marketing must be at least in some part technologically innovative products.

However, although it is not hard to show the fulfilment of the necessary condition (complementarity of the processes), the situation with sufficient conditions is not so straightforward due to the lack of required data confirming the formulated statement directly.

Therefore, checking the sufficient condition, we assumed that it is met if there are substantial shifts in the values of the indicators characterising each of the innovative processes when switching from their innovation cores to sub-core.

Fixing these shifts for Russian and foreign-owned enterprises allows us to conclude that there is interdependence between innovation processes for creating technological and marketing innovations, that is, they are related for firms of two types of property. Moreover, the relationship works in both directions: the marketing innovation affects the parameters of technological innovation and vice versa.

At the same time, the difference in the direction and character of shifts in values of the indicators mentioned above of technological and marketing innovation shows the divergence in the behaviour strategies of companies of two ownership forms. The first difference is related to the type of innovative products whose distribution needs to be supported by marketing innovations. The second one is determined by the kind of market in which enterprises use marketing innovations stimulating demand for their products.

It is generally assumed in the literature that marketing innovation is a key driver of firm's innovation activity (Bartoloni, 2016). However, this is not always the case for Russian industrial enterprises. Speaking about the technologically innovative products supported by marketing innovations, it is worth noting that enterprises of each of the considered forms of ownership use marketing innovations to promote products that are radically new to the Russian market. However, foreign-owned enterprises are in a more favourable position compared to Russian enterprises. They can economize on marketing innovation when promoting products new to the Russian market, but known to the external market.

As for choosing the type of market for more intensive investment in marketing innovations, the market of non-innovative products seems to be the most relevant for foreign-owned enterprises. It confirms the fact that foreign-owned enterprises that are not involved in the creation of technological innovations, that is, the

enterprises on the pure marketing-innovation core, have a cost-intensity of marketing innovation four times higher than Russian-owned enterprises.

Among the reasons for such differences, the degree of firms' orientation towards the export is the most attention-getting. The following measures can help smooth the differences. The first one is to create favourable conditions for the abroad economic activity of domestic enterprises. The second is to strengthen the competitive environment, stimulate the improvement of the quality of innovative products at local markets. The measures of the first dimension include the creation of preferential conditions for enterprises exporting innovative products, for example, through the state-level tax breaks or introducing preferential prices for some domestic production factors regulated by the government. The second dimension measures strengthening the competitive environment comprise reducing barriers for new players entering local markets. Participation in international trade and developing a competitive environment in the domestic market will generate incentives to improve the quality of technological innovations created by domestic enterprises and to activate the concurrent process of creating and applying marketing innovations.

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